

CHALLENGES OF TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: Nowadays interpretation of phraseological units is an critical subject for modern interpretation thinks about. The logical distribution incorporates data around the basic interpretation methods of phraseological units that are essentially topical for the modern translatology. The author depicts diverse focuses of see of the popular etymologists and translatalogists who examined this vital issue.

Key words: *translatology, lexical combinations, stock phrases, interpreter, translatalogists, target content, phraseological collocations, enthusiastic, classification, misinterpretation.*

Translation of phraseological units is topical for the contemporary translatology nowadays. According to many outstanding specialists, phraseological units are lexical combinations, the meaning of which is defined by the whole expression. The most distinctive feature of phraseological unit is its emotional expressiveness and conciseness of thought expression. Fairly often, phraseological units are functioning in the newspaper style. It should be noted that phraseological units are very often transformed into „stock phrases“. Defining phraseological units in the text the ability to find an equivalent to it during the translation process is the most important stage for the translator. In order to translate a phraseological unit, the translator should use phraseological dictionaries and context plays an important role during the translation process. In conclusion it should be noted that phraseological units reflect culture and a national mentality of a definite nation. Due to this reason, translation of phraseological units is one of the topical issues for the contemporary translatology. Phraseological units are an integral part of any language or culture and knowing these units and appropriate interpretation of them is an evidence of appropriate translation of the whole expression or a work of art.

The logical distribution incorporates data approximately the basic interpretation methods of phraseological units that are essentially topical for the modern translation studies. The creator describes different focuses of see of the celebrated etymologists and translators who dissected this vital issue.

Nowadays interpretation of phraseological units is an critical subject for modern translation studies. Subsequently, this subject is being talked about by translatalogists and it is closely associated with the fact that interpreter ought to translate the meaning of the full expression or a gather of words and the essential errand for the interpreter is to select an important identical for the satisfactory interpretation of a definite phraseological unit amid the interpretation prepare. The interpreter ought to characterize the ways of translation and express the connotative and assessment capacities of the total expression. It is expedient, according to our opinion, to give an accurate definition to the notion of phraseological unit proposed by A. V. Koonin "Phraseological unit is a separable combinability of words with the analyzed meaning and a definite stability at a phraseological level"²¹.

²¹ Kuzmin, S. S. Idiomatic Translation from Russian into English (Theory and Practice). –Moscow, 2007, pp. 7-291.

Numerous celebrated and extraordinary translatoologists consider that phraseological units are “translator’s wrong companions”, which speak to a few phraseological units of the source content and these phraseological units in entirety or in portion coincide with the units of the target content and the examined phraseological units can make untrue affiliations amid the interpretation handle due to the reason of their closeness with free collocations. Phraseological units – “translator’s wrong companions” - have a positive meaning and this meaning can unquestionably or especially contrast from the meaning of a phraseological unit within the target content. Agreeing to a celebrated translator V.N. Komissarov, a few phraseological units can have a place to the “translator’s untrue companions” due to the reality that examined phraseological units have a comparative shape which makes it troublesome to choose a satisfactory identical within the other dialect²².

The foremost pertinent reason is it her among spurred or opaque phraseological units. For illustration, phraseological unit compares to the Russian phraseological unit “трусить, малодушничать, бояться”, and the taking after phraseological unit “to lead smb. by the nose” ought to be deciphered into the Russian dialect as “вести кого-либо на поводу”²³.

With respect to numerous language specialists, phraseological units are word combinations, the meaning of which is characterized agreeing to the total expression but not concurring to their components or dialect parts. With connection to notional component authoritative, phraseological units ought to be isolated into metaphorical and non metaphorical. Non-metaphorical phraseological units are called as phraseological collocations. Analysing these phraseological units, we mention that their language components express their meaning, but these units collocate with definite words and the translator cannot change them: “принимать меры” – “to take measures”, “принимать решение” – “to make a decision”²⁴.

Thus, there’s a require within the examination of a few ways of nontranslation, expounded by a popular translator V.S. Slepovich:

1) interpretation of phraseological units can be prepared on the premise of existing English collocation:

“рисковать” – “to take a chance”, “отдыхать” - “to have a rest”, “обедиться” – “to take offence”, “вздремнуть” – “to take a nap”.

2) With the help of equivalentents (definite and indefinite):

“попасть в цель” – “to hit the target”, “положить конец чему-либо” – “to put an end to smth.”, “читат между строк” – “to read between lines”, “принимать во внимание” – “to take into account”, “обратить особое внимание” – “to make a point”, “делать поспешные выводы” – “to jump at conclusions”, “взлеты и падения” – “ups - and - downs”²⁵.

The following sort of phraseological units is metaphorical. For this reason, metaphorical phraseological units are known as expressions. As we know, expression may be a language

²² Komissarov, V. N., Korolova, A. L. Practical Manual on the Translation from English into Russian. – Moscow, 1999, p 14.

²³ Komissarov, V. N., Korolova, A. L. Practical Manual on the Translation from English into Russian. – Moscow, 1999, p 14.

²⁴ Slepovich, V. S. Translation Manual (the English and the Russian Languages). –Minsk, 2005, pp. 74-79.

²⁵ Slepovich, V. S. Translation Manual (the English and the Russian Languages). –Minsk, 2005, pp. 74-79.

expression, the meaning of which isn't the sum of implications constituting their components. For example, in the Russian language there are some idioms like: “погнаться за двумя зайцами”, “попасть как кур в очки”, “кишка тонка”, “бить баклуши”, “сем пятниц на неделе”, “кот наплакал”, “как зеницу ока”, “бить ключом”, “попадать впросак”, “без сучка без задоринки” and the translation of the abovementioned idioms into the English language: “try to kill two birds with one stone”, “not to have the guts”, “to twiddle one's thumbs”, “rain at seven, fine at eleven”, “as scarce as hen's teeth”, “like the apple of one's eye”, “to be in full swing”, “to make a fool of (oneself)”, and “as clean as a whistle”. As a rule, the show, an dissected expression “to twiddle one's thumbs” is utilized in political addresses and daily paper fashion.

It should be pointed out that interpretation correspondences within the target dialect are utilized for the interpretation of expressions:

1) translation with the help of absolute equivalents: “лить крокодиловы слезы” – “to shed crocodile tears”, “подсластить пилюлю” – “to sugar the pill”, “львиная доля” – “lion's share”, “играть с огнем” – “to play with fire”²⁶.

Enthusiastic expressiveness and brevity of in spite of the fact that expression are the foremost particular highlights of phraseological units. Phraseological units are working within the daily paper fashion, eminently in the newspaper features due to the truth that daily paper features are expressive and brief. As a rule, newspaper features snatch consideration and reflect the state of mind towards the occasions described in the article.

Phraseological units and their utilize in both verbal and composed dialect can be utilized regularly (normatively) and sometimes. The common meaning of phraseological units is the meaning shown within the lexicon. Incidental meaning is the meaning that phraseological unit gets in any setting, went with by a takeoff from the standard and by and large acknowledged.

Among different issues that cutting edge etymology ponders, examining national — social specifics of dialects plays an critical part. The dialect is the major way of arrangement and presence of man's information approximately the world. Firstly, it is the premise for the improvement of phonetic picture of the world, one of the most profound layers of the picture of the world.

In conjunction with relative reciprocals where deficient compliance of units is watched, there are interlingual components, completely not coincident among themselves. In our case phraseological units of one dialect have no phraseological conformities in other dialects.

The classification proposed by Academician V. V. Vinogradov was received in a number of works on expressiveness, counting in works given to phraseological units of the English dialect (of which it ought to be famous the capital „English-Russian Phraseological Dictionary“ compiled by A. V. Kunin.

Subsequently, drawing the conclusion to the abovementioned data, it ought to be famous that interpretation of phraseological units is the foremost vital and or maybe troublesome errand for the interpreter. The reason is that interpreters ought to pay their consideration to the coincidence of presentive and coherent meanings of phraseological units within the source and target dialects amid the interpretation forms and sorts of settings in which they are working. Be that as it may, misfortune and alter of complex or connotative capacities of phraseological units

²⁶ Kuzmin, S. S. Translators Russian-English Phraseological Dictionary. –Moscow, 2006, p. 776.

can be the result of misinterpretation of an figure of speech or the complete expression within the target dialect.

In conclusion, it can be said that there are enough difficulties and complications to be faced in the field of translation studies. However, in some sensitive situations, the application of professionalism is one of the important tasks before the translator. In particular, after installing new leather seats on the planes of the American Airlines company, they announced to their Mexican customers “Fly on leather!” reported. But when the phrase was translated into Spanish, “Fly without clothes!” expressed the meaning. Thus, “American Airlines” airline company faced an unfavorable situation. Also, the famous American beer production company Coors has launched “Turn It Loose!” He showed his advertisement with the slogan (“So, be free!”). However, when this phrase is translated into Spanish, it means “Drink up and get better”. Accordingly, it has a different meaning in such situations.